

Clinical Outcome and Recurrence Following Single Burr Hole Evacuation in Patients with Chronic Subdural Hematoma (CSDH)

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Abstract:

Introduction: Chronic subdural hematoma (CSDH) is one of the most common neurosurgical cases. A reported incidence of 17.6/100,000/year has more than doubled in the past 25 years in parallel with an aging population. Surgical drainage is the mainstay of treatment, with variable recurrence risks. The purpose of this study is to assess the clinical outcome and recurrence following single burr hole drainage of CSDH patients in our centre.

Methods: It is a retrospective study which was conducted in the Department of Neurosurgery, CN Center, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital from January 2023 to December 2023. In our study we included 80 patients, age group from 21-90 years (mean 59.1 years). All patients were managed with single burr hole evacuation of Chronic SDH. Postoperatively patients were kept in supine position without pillow for 48 hours.

Inclusion Criteria: Symptomatic presence of CSDH on the NCCT head.

Exclusion Criteria: (1) Presence of acute SDH. (2) Craniotomies with primary etiology other than an SDH (e.g., abscess drainage, tumor resection). (3) Unknown patients. (4) Patients with missing information.

Results: Preoperative and postoperative neurological statuses of the patients were recorded as per Glasgow outcome scale. Out of 80 patients (mean age: 59.1 years; range: 21-90 years; male: 51; female: 29) with CSDH underwent single burr hole drainage with peri-procedural mortality and morbidity were 1.25%(n=1) and 2.5% (n=2), respectively. Overall, among our patient population, recurrence was seen in 7.5% (n=6). The mean total hospital stay was 3.5±1.5 days.

Conclusions: The study showed single burr hole drainage for chronic SDH evacuation showed satisfactory level of resolution of hematoma and clinical and neurological improvement and acceptable level of recurrence and it is safe and effective with acceptable level of cost.

Keywords: Subdural, Hematoma, NCCT head, Burr Hole.

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Introduction

Chronic subdural hematoma (CSDH) is defined as a cystic unclotted hematoma within the outer and inner membranes in the subdural space [1]. It is usually affecting the elderly population and one of the most common condition encountered in neurosurgical practice daily [2,3,4]. Subacute SDH develops from 3 days to 3 weeks after head injury, and chronic SDH that appears more than 3 weeks after injury [2,3]. CSDH, it forms gradually following hemorrhage from bridging parasagittal veins following head trauma. A minor trauma may cause CSDH in patients with comorbid conditions like epilepsy, hematological disorders, cerebral atrophy, and under anticoagulant therapy, chronic alcoholism. The most common presenting symptoms of CSDH are headache, unconsciousness, confusion, and neurological deficits (contralateral motor deficits) [2]. In CSDH,

indications for surgical evacuation of the hematoma are focal neurological deficit, mental status changes, unilateral weakness, when the thickness of the hematoma becomes 1cm or more, or if there is progressive increase in size on serial imaging (CT or MRI) [4]. Patients with CSDH, evacuation of hematoma can be evacuated by various surgical procedures. It includes: (a) two burr holes method and irrigating check with tepid saline until the fluid runs clear; (b) single large burr hole with irrigation and aspiration; (c) single burr hole drainage with placement of subdural drain; (d) twist drill craniostomy and (e) formal craniotomy with excision of subdural membrane (membranectomy) [3]. All of the abovementioned procedures can be done under general or local, anaesthesia depending on the hospital protocol or the preference of the surgeon [3,4,5].

Evacuation of hematoma surgically for CSDH is one of the commonest procedures which can be performed safely by a neurosurgery or general surgery resident. The surgical procedure can be performed under local anaesthesia, monitored anaesthesia care [6] or under general anaesthesia. No consensus yet exists regarding the optimal surgical technique to treat the CSDH, though CSDH is one of the most common neurosurgery conditions [7].

Materials and Method

Study Setting: The study was conducted retrospectively at the Department of Neurosurgery, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital, a reputed medical institution equipped with the necessary infrastructure to facilitate extensive research on Chronic Subdural Hematoma.

Duration of the Study: This research encapsulated a span of 1 year, providing a substantial timeframe to gather, analyse and interpret data pertinent to the clinical presentation and surgical outcomes of Chronic Subdural Hematoma.

Sample Size: A total of 80 cases were selected for this study, ensuring a comprehensive analysis while maintaining a focus on detailed individual case evaluations.

Study Design: A retrospective study design was employed to scrutinize the medical records of patients who underwent single burr hole for Chronic Subdural Hematoma within the stipulated study period.

Data Collection

Medical Records Review: A meticulous review of medical records was undertaken to collect data on the clinical presentation and surgical outcomes of patients. The data sourced included:

1. **Demographic Information:** Age, gender, and other relevant demographic details of the patients.
2. **Clinical Presentation:** Details pertaining to the symptoms exhibited by patients at the time of presentation physical signs, and other relevant clinical indicators.
3. **Diagnostic Procedures:** Information on the diagnostic procedures employed, including imaging studies such as CT scan, MRI Brain.
4. **Surgical Details:** Records of the surgical procedures, surgical techniques, and any intraoperative complications.

Surgical Outcome Evaluation: A thorough evaluation of surgical outcomes was conducted based on the following parameters:

1. **Post-operative Recovery:** Data on the immediate post-operative recovery of patients, noting any complications or adverse events.

2. **Long-term Outcomes:** Information on the long-term outcomes of the surgeries, including overall patient prognosis.

Data Analysis: Data obtained from the medical records were organized and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. The analysis included:

1. **Descriptive Statistics:** Utilized to summarize the demographic data and clinical presentation of the patients.
2. **Outcome Analysis:** Employed to evaluate the surgical outcomes

Ethical Considerations: The study was conducted following the ethical guidelines pertaining to retrospective studies, ensuring the confidentiality and privacy of patient data at all stages of the research.

Results

It is a retrospective study which was conducted in the Department of Neurosurgery, CN Center, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital from January 2023 to December 2023. In our study we included 80 patients (Male 51, Female 29), age group from 21-90 years (mean 59.1 years). Preoperatively outcome was explained to the patient and family members regarding the outcomes of the surgical treatment. All patients were managed with a single burr hole evacuation of chronic SDH. The wound was closed in layers and number 10 feeding tube drain was placed subdural position in all cases. Post operatively patients were treated with injectable antibiotics, antiepileptic and analgesics for 3-4 days and patients were discharged with oral antibiotics for 5 days.

After taking detailed history and neurological examination of all patients, the diagnosis of CSDH was confirmed with either CT scan. All the patients were operated in supine position in operating table and the involved side of the head was prepared by shaving the hair.

During the procedure ECG, oxygen saturation as well as blood pressure were monitored, and 100% oxygen was administered via nasal catheter. The operating site was cleaned using savlon solution, alcohol and povidone antiseptic solutions and draped in the usual manner. Prophylactic intravenous ceftriaxone 1gm was given just prior to skin incision. 2% lignocaine with adrenaline of 10 to 20 cc was administered to the scalp incision site. We use IV sedatives, like Haloperidol and Promethazine, Midazolam according to weight of the patients those who were restless and uncooperative from alteration of mentation.

After that we checked for pain sensation and a 4 to 6 cm linear scalp incision was made over the parietal prominence, pericranium retracted and the skull bone was exposed. Using Hudson brace hand

drill we made a single burr hole, the dura was cauterized and the dura was opened with a cruciate incision. After opening the dura, dark coloured hemolyzed blood comes out under pressure and evacuated by inserting soft flexible number 10 paediatric feeding tube. After evacuation of the hematoma, the subdural space was irrigated with warm normal saline until clear irrigating fluid was returned. In the end, the subdural space was filled again with normal saline to displace the air from the subdural space. The feeding tube drain left in subdural space passing through a separate scalp incision. The scalp incision was closed with interrupted silk stitch. The feeding tube drain was connected to closed system collecting bag which is usually a sterile urine bag.

Postoperatively, all the patients were monitored in post-operative ICU care system. All the patients

were kept in supine position without pillow for 48 hours with the collecting draining bag placed 40-50 cm below from the patient's head. Drain was removed when there was no further fluid coming out and accumulated in the draining bag or nil to the amount of 10 to 20cc. Most of the patients were discharged from the hospital on the 3rd or 4th postoperative day and stitches were removed on the 10th postoperative day at local hospital. The first postoperative follow-up was done on the 14th postoperative day, the second visit at 30th postoperative day and finally at 3 months. At last visit patients were advised regarding danger signs and advised them to come back if there are any new symptoms. The clinical status of the patients at the last postoperative follow-up was assessed using the Glasgow Outcome Score.

Table 1: Glasgow Outcome Score

Score	Grade	Description
5	Good recovery	Normal or near normal recovery
4	Moderate disability	Disabled but independent
3	Severe disability	Dependant with physical or psychological disabilities or both
2	Vegetative state	
1	Death	

Table 2: Demographic characteristics of patients

Age group	Frequency	Percentage
21-30 years	0	0
31-40 years	5	6.25
41-50 years	8	10
51-60 years	18	22.5
61-70 years	26	32.5
71-80 years	12	15
>81 years	11	13.75
Gender		
Male	51	64%
Female	29	36%

In our study, 51(64%) were of males, and 29(36%) were of female patients with a M:F ratio of 1.78:1. According to age categorization, CSDH was most common in the age group 61-70 years (32%), followed by 51-60 years (22.5%), 71-80 years (15%), above 80 years (13.75%), 41-50 years (10%) and 31-40 years (6.25%). The age range was 21 years to 90 years old with the mean age of 59.1.

Table 3: Risk factors associated with the studied patients

Risk factor	Number of patients	Percentage
Trauma	31	38.75
H/o coagulopathy and Anticoagulant use	18	22.5
Alcohol related diseases	12	15
T2 DM	11	13.75
None	8	10

Analyzing the risk factors for Chronic subdural hematoma revealed trauma was the predominant cause, observed in 38.75% of the patients, out of 31 trauma induced CSDH, 23 were male and 8 were female, so male had 3 times higher risk of developing traumatic CSDH than female, followed by coagulopathy and anticoagulant use in 22.5%, alcohol related disease in 15%, T2 DM in 13.75% and no definite cause was found in 10% cases.

Table 4: Presenting symptoms of patients

Symptoms	Frequency	Percentage
Headache	62	77.5
Unilateral weakness	54	67.5
Convulsion	7	8.75
Speech disturbance	6	7.5
Recent memory loss	4	5
Sphincter disturbance	4	5

In our study group headache was the most common presenting symptom which was present in 77.5% of the patients. Other presenting symptoms included unilateral weakness in 54(67.5%), convulsion in 7 (8.75%), speech disturbance in 6(7.5%), recent

memory loss 4(5%) and sphincter disturbance 4(5%) of the patients. History of head trauma prior to presentation was documented in 31 (38.75%) patients, 49 (61.25%) of the patients in this study had no obvious history of head trauma.

Table 5: Site of Chronic subdural hematoma

Site	Frequency	Percentage
Right	21	26.25
Left	32	40
Bilateral	27	33.75

All of our patients were diagnosed with head CT scan. Based on the imaging findings, 32(40%) patients had a left side hematoma, 21(26.25%) of patients had a right side and 27(33.75%) patients had bilateral CSDH. Two patients were died on the same of operation and one patient was under ICU care for 17 days due to some other comorbidities. Making the mean hospital stay 3 to 4 days.

Table 6: Preoperative presenting GCS of studied patients

Glasgow coma scale	Number of patients	Percentage
13-15	62	77.5
9-12	10	12.5
3-8	8	10
Total	80	100

In our study group most of the patients were GCS between 13-15 (77.5%), followed by 9-12 (12.5%) and 3-8 (10%).

Table 7: Post-operative complications

Complications	Number of patients	Percentage
Recurrence	6	7.5
Surgical site infection	3	3.75
Cortical bleed	2	2.5
Seizure	1	1.25

Recurrence was the most common complication which was found in 7.5% patients, which was managed with immediate reoperation through the same burr hole. Other complications were surgical site infection, cortical bleed and seizure which were found 3.75%, 2.5% and 1.25% respectively.

Table 8: Recurrence associated with comorbidities

Comorbidities	Number of patients	Percentage
Anticoagulant use	4	66.6
Repeated history of trauma	1	16.6
Alcohol related disease	1	16.6

Anticoagulant use was the most common risk factor for recurrence of chronic SDH which was found in 4 out of 6 patients (66.6%) followed by repeated history of trauma in one patient and alcohol related disease in one patient. All the patients were managed with immediate reoperation through same burr hole followed by taking consultation with other departments.

Table 9: Postoperative outcome evaluation

Glasgow outcome score	Frequency	Percentage
5	69	86.25
4	8	10
3	1	1.25
2	0	0
1	2	2.5

In our study, postoperative outcome was assessed using Glasgow Outcome Score at the last postoperative follow-up. 86.25% of our patients reported a good recovery at the end of the 3 months following operation 69(86.25%) reported good recovery with resumption of normal life (GOS 5) while 8(10%) reported moderate disability (GOS 4). 1 patient had persistent (GOS 3), and there were no patients with GOS of 2. Death occurred in 2 (2.5%) of our patients.

Traumatic CSDH patients had a better postoperative outcome with GOS 4 and 5, than those with non-traumatic CSDH and death was more common in patients with non-traumatic CSDH. 2 patients were died in our study with spontaneous CSDH with other comorbidities with no history of trauma. Reoperation was done for recollection on 6(7.5%) patients, and the hematoma was evacuated through the same burr hole. Patients were improved after reoperation and were discharged after improvement. No other postoperative complications were observed in our study.

Discussion

Chronic subdural hematoma is a common neurosurgical condition that is encountered in day to day practice. The surgical evacuation of CSDH can be performed by Neurosurgeon and General Surgeon and its residents. Operative management of CSDH can be performed safely with the institutional resources in rural facilities by general surgeons those who are familiar with the procedure [15].

In our study, CSDH was more common in men than in women. Of the 80 patients operated, 51(64%) were male, and 29(36%) were female patients with M:F ratio of 1.76:1. Male predominance was also found in other studies like [8], [9], [10] and [11]. The mean age at presentation in this study was 59.1, with 67(83.75%) of the patients were above 51 years of age. CSDH occurs predominantly in the elderly population [3,4,5,7,8,9,10,11].

The most common presenting symptom of the patients was headache followed by unilateral weakness, convulsion, speech disturbance, recent memory loss and sphincter disturbance. History of head trauma was documented in 38.75% patients which is similar to other study results [2, 9, 10, 11].

In our study, 40% of the patients had a left side hematoma, and 26.25% had right sided hematoma. Bilateral CSDH was found in 33.75% patients.

All of our patients were treated with a single burr hole evacuation with intraoperative irrigation and postoperative subdural closed system drainage. Single burr hole craniostomy is the most effective procedure [12,13]. The mean hospital stay in our study was 3.5±1.5 days which is almost similar to other studies for the same procedure (13). In our study 77 (96.25%) of our patients had good recovery, GOS 4 and GOS 5, at the time of their last postoperative visit, and there were 2 (2.5%) deaths which is similar with other study [11].

The criteria for the early recurrent CSDH are the return of symptoms or re accumulation of the hematoma after a surgery within 3 months regardless of the location, amount or repeated operations [14]. In our study recurrence was occurred in 6(7.5%) patients which is similar to other studies [8,9,11]. All the patients with recurrent subdural hematoma were treated with evacuation of the hematoma through the same burr hole. Burr hole craniostomy is the most effective procedure in treating recurrent hematoma and craniotomy was reserved for last choice of treatment [12].

In this study, postoperative outcome was worse in patients with non-traumatic CSDH. There was no significant association between postoperative outcome with sex and age of patients.

Conclusion

Single burr-hole craniostomy and closed system subdural drainage of CSDH under local anesthesia is an easy, safe and effective technique for the treatment of CSDH which can be performed in primary level hospital. It is a lifesaving procedure for the treatment of CSDH though it is notorious for recurrence.

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